

Spectroscopic and Magnetic Studies on Acetylsalicylhydrazone Metal Complexes

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Acid hydrazides and hydrazones are interesting chelating agents¹. Hydrazone derivatives are used as fungicides and in the treatment of diseases such as tuberculosis, leprosy and mental disorders². Saha and co-workers³ reported Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with some hydrazone derivatives. Metal complexes of divalent transition metal ions with hydrazone derived from salicylaldehyde and salicylic acid hydrazide were investigated⁴. A series of transition metal complexes of Schiff base hydrazones were prepared⁵. Some transition complexes of heterocyclic hydrazones⁶ and benzoyl salicylhydrazone⁷ have been reported.

The present communication reports the structural study of the complexes of acetylsalicylhydrazone (ASH) with some transition metal ions, such as Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic susceptibility values (Table 1) indicate that all the complexes are paramagnetic and spin-free.

The electronic spectra of the prepared complexes (Table 1) were recorded and no absorption features were observed for the ligand in the studied range. The electronic spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex reveals broad overlapping peaks centered at 13 966 cm⁻¹. The spectrum suggests that Cu^{II} has an octahedral environment and broadening observed in the spectrum is attributed to Jahn-Teller effect⁸. The spectra of Ni^{II} and Cr^{III} showed well defined bands, such bands were attributed to spin-allowed or spin-forbidden transitions. The crystal field parameters 10Dq and B were calculated using equations : $v_1 = 10Dq$; $v_3 = 12Dq + 15B$. The peak positions and crystal field parameters indicate

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE OF ACETYL SALICYLHYDRAZONE (ASH) COMPLEXES

Compd. / (Colour)	Metal% : Found/(Calcd.)	λ_{max} cm ⁻¹	Assignment	Dq	B	μ_{eff} B.M.	Cond. $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in DMF
[Cu.L.3H ₂ O]Cl (Green)	19.24 (19.25)	13 968	${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$			1.95	43
[Ni.L.3H ₂ O]Cl (Green)	18.18 (18.05)	11 792 12 820 19 658 29 069	${}^3A_{2g} \xrightarrow{v_1} {}^3T_{1g}$ ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1E_{2g}$ ${}^3A_{2g} \xrightarrow{v_2} {}^3T_{2g}$ ${}^3A_{2g} \xrightarrow{v_3} {}^3T_{1g}(P)$	11792	994	2.98	41
[Co.L.3H ₂ O]Cl (Brown)	18.10 (18.11)	14 705 18 382	${}^4T_{1g} \xrightarrow{v_2} {}^4A_{2g}$ ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$	8169	898	4.55	40
[Fe.L.3H ₂ O]Cl ₂ (Brown)	15.60 (15.61)	13 368 17 730 23 809 27 777	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G), {}^4E_g(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$	1164	766	5.89	68
[Mn.L.3H ₂ O]Cl (Buff)	17.10 (17.09)	19 531 21 929 27 777	${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$ ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$	7290	729	5.85	39
[Cr.L.3H ₂ O]Cl ₂ (Orange)	14.70 (14.69)	12 020 16 077 18 248 20 000 24 752 39 864	${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ ${}^4A_{2g} \xrightarrow{v_1} {}^4T_{1g}$ ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}$ ${}^4A_{2g} \xrightarrow{v_2} {}^4T_{2g}$ ${}^4A_{2g} \xrightarrow{v_3} {}^4T_{2g}(P)$	17162	684	3.86	60

TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF ACETYL SALICYLHYDRAZONE (ASH) AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES

Ligand ASH	Cr-ASH	Mn-ASH	Fe-ASH	Co-ASH	Ni-ASH	Cu-ASH	Assignment
—	3 325	—	3 350	3 350	—	3 430	VOH coordinated
—	—	3 210	—	—	3 250	3 220	water
3 150	—	3 130	—	3 120	—	3 110	VNH + VOH
2 900	2 900	2 900	—	2 850	2 880	2 905	VCH, VCH ₃
2 745	2 750	2 730	2 750	2 750	2 735	2 730	VCH, aldehyde proton
1 660	1 650	1 651	1 652	1 649	1 648	1 630	VC=O (amide I)
1 610	1 600	1 601	1 603	1 600	1 600	1 595	VC=N
1 565	1 562	1 560	1 562	1 560	1 560	1 557	VNH (amide II)
1 380	1 375	1 385	1 375	1 460	1 370	1 370	δ _{NH} + ν _{CN} (amide III)
—	770	770	790	770	780	775	ρ _l (H ₂ O)

that the Ni^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes have octahedral structure. The spectrum of the Co^{II} complex contains two peaks at 14 705 and 18 382 cm⁻¹, assigned to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴A_{2g} and ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g(P)} respectively. The electronic spectral parameters 10 *Dq* and *B* values were estimated using the relationships⁸: $\nu_2 = 18Dq$; $\nu_3 = 6Dq + 15B$. The spectra of the Mn^{II} and Fe^{III} complexes reveal overlapping peaks, having absorption features attributed to spin-forbidden transitions. Tanabe-Sugano diagrams⁸ were used for the calculation of 10 *Dq* and *B* values.

All the complexes react with AgNO₃ forming a white precipitate which indicates the cationic nature of the complexes. The complexes were studied using conductometric titration and molar conductance. The results indicate the formation of 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 (ligand : metal) complexes⁹. The molar conductance data (Table 1) indicate that the divalent complexes contain two ions, while trivalent metal complexes possess three ions¹⁰.

The main absorption frequencies in the infrared spectra of the ligand and metal chelates are listed in Table 2. The ligand shows characteristic frequencies due to ν_{C=O}, ν_{C=N}, ν_{OH} and ν_{NH}. The ligand has three coordination sites and the presence of several bonding sites is likely to give stability to metal complexes. On comparing the spectra of the ligand and metal chelates, the spectra of the Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes show disappearance of ν_{C=O} band and the presence of new bands which can be attributed to OH group. This indicates that the ligand is coordinated in the enol form. Also, the comparison reveals a shift in ν_{C=O} and ν_{C=N} to lower frequency upon complexation. The decrease in frequencies indicates that coordination takes place through phenolic oxygen, C=N and OH in the spectra of all complexes (Table 2). The spectra of the Co^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes reveal carbonyl group, which implies that the coordination sites may be C=O, C=N and the phenolic oxygen. In the high frequency region of the metal chelates can attributed to coordinated water molecules¹¹. Also, coordinated water molecules are expected to show other modes in the low frequency region; the rocking mode of coordinated water is observed in the region 770–790 cm⁻¹ as it was reported earlier for ruthenium-aquo complexes¹².

Temperature dependence of electrical conductivity data

reveal a linear trend with inflection appearing at 336 K in the ligand conductivity. Such inflection was absent in the conductivity of complexes. It is found that the general behaviour of electrical conductivity obeys the equation: $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E/kT)$, the symbols having usual significance. The values of electrical conductivities (σ) are listed in Table 3. They lie in the range of typical semiconductors¹³. The break observed for the ligand in the plot indicates phase transition and two different activation energies are listed in Table 3. Also, it is observed from the plot that the phase conducting in the lower temperature range is of lower energy (*E*₁) than in the higher temperature range (*E*₂). This phase transition observed is most probably associated with two molecular structures which exchange conduction at different thermal stabilities¹⁴. Metal chelates exhibit a conventional semiconducting behaviour and conductivity shows tendency to increase by raising the temperature⁹. The conductivity of complexes is lower than that for ligand, so the ligand possess higher conjugated structure. The lower conductivity of complexes is mainly due to the formation of stable complexes which localised the electrons around the hydrazone molecule¹⁵. For metal chelates, the small activation energy observed may be attributed to the interaction between the electrons of *d*-orbitals and the π -orbitals of the ligand. This interaction will localise the π -electronic change on the ligand molecule. It is clear that the activation energy is reduced after complex formation to about 0.04 eV, which means that the observed electrical values using band theory is approximate. The presence of metal cation create an impurity level between the conduction and valence band (as *n* or *p* semiconductors)¹⁶.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF ACTIVATION ENERGIES, ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF ACETYL SALICYLHYDRAZONE (ASH) AND ITS METAL CHELATES

Compd.	<i>T</i> _c K	<i>E</i> ₁ eV	<i>E</i> ₂ eV	σ_1 Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ at 298 K	σ_2 Ω ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹ at 416 K
(ASH) ligand	336	0.25	0.78	6.21 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	3.07 × 10 ⁻⁸
Cr-chelate	—	0.04	—	5.62 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	9.26 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
Mn-chelate	—	0.04	—	2.28 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	3.77 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
Co-chelate	—	0.04	—	3.77 × 10 ⁻¹⁰	5.08 × 10 ⁻¹⁰

Experimental

All chemicals used were of pure grade (Merck and B.D.H.). Acetylsalicylhydrazone (m.p. 200–205°) was prepared by condensing salicylaldehyde with acetic acid hydrazide¹⁷. Metal complexes were prepared by refluxing aqueous ethanolic solutions of the ligand and metal chlorides in 1 : 1 ratio for 2 h. After cooling, the complexes were washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were chemically analysed. Magnetic susceptibility was measured at room temperature using Gouy method¹⁸, and the effective magnetic moment from relation¹⁴, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84\sqrt{X_m - T}$, where T is the absolute temperature.

The molar ratio of the different complexes was titrated using a Cole-Parmer 5800-05 conductivity meter. Solutions of acetylsalicylhydrazone (0.01 M) and metal chlorides (5×10^{-4} M) were prepared in ethanol. ASH solution was titrated against metal ion solutions. Molar conductance of the complexes was measured in DMF.

Ir spectra were recorded using a Shimadzu IR 440 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (DMF) on a Perkin-Elmer λ 3b spectrophotometer. The electrical conductivity (d.c.) was measured as a function of temperature (298–450 K) using the reported method²⁰. The samples were arranged between two copper electrodes. All the samples were compressed to pellets (13 mm dia \times 1 mm) using a pressure of 6 ton cm^{-2} . The data were obtained using Thander Tm 353 and HC 3500 T multimeters.

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